

Informed Consent Form (ICF)

I declare that I am over 18 years old and agree to participate in studies conducted by *<include research team name/research team responsible>* from *<research team should specify the laboratory/ university>*. These studies aim to understand software technology's feasibility, viability, and experience using the Technology Probe methodology.

Procedures

Various software technologies may be presented. I understand that I will be taught how technology works and asked to use it during the session organized by the researcher. In this session, some experimental methods will be applied, and I will be asked to complete some tasks to reflect on their use and evaluate them. I understand that once the session has ended, the opinions I expressed and the questionnaires I answered will be studied to understand the aspects of the software technology presented to me.

The researcher will conduct the study by collecting, analyzing, and reporting data collected throughout the session. I understand that I am not obligated to provide information regarding my performance in the session and that I may request the removal of my results from the study at any time without penalty. I understand that there will be no reward for participating in this study and that my decision not to participate will not negatively impact me. I also understand that once the data is collected and analyzed, my name will be removed from the data and will not be used during the analysis or in the presentation of the results.

Confidentiality

All information collected in this study is confidential and follows the principles of *<research team should specify applicable data protection regulations, e.g., GDPR, LGPD>*. My name will not be identified at any time. Likewise, I commit not to disclose my results until the study is completed and to maintain confidentiality regarding the techniques and documents presented that are part of the experiment.

Benefits and Right to Withdraw

I understand that this study does not pose any personal risk and that the benefits I will receive from participating are limited to learning about the proposed software technology. However, the researchers hope to gain insights into the software technology's feasibility, viability, and experience.

I understand that I am free to ask questions at any time or request that any personal information related to me not be included in the study. I am participating voluntarily, solely to contribute to the advancement and development of software technology.

Responsible

<complete with the name of the research team responsible>

<complete with the person affiliation>

Consent Statement

By signing below, you acknowledge that you have read and understood this form and voluntarily agree to participate in the study.

Participant's Name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

For the research team to fill - **ID:** _____